

**ANALYSIS OF METHODS AND ALGORITHMS FOR KEYWORD
EXTRACTION**

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Abstract: This article discusses methods and algorithms for keyword extraction in text mining. It classifies keyword extraction methods and comparatively describes the main keyword extraction algorithms. It is concluded that it is necessary to develop an objective and universal criterion for assessing the quality of work of keyword extraction algorithms.

Key words: Key words, key phrases, text analysis (morphological, lexical, syntactic, pragmatic), dictionary, corpus, ontology

Introduction

The task of text analysis is based on algorithms for extracting keywords from texts. The result is sophisticated natural language text processing software solutions. Keywords are important words or phrases that well describe the content of a text document and allow you to identify its topic. A set of keywords (KW) extracted from the text can act as metadata. It helps solve problems of search, classification, clustering, interpretation and summarization of information [8]. It is necessary to rely on effective algorithms when developing automated systems that perform the task of extracting KW. Because there is clear and verified information about their performance and application limits. This article deals primarily with the Uzbek language, which has a

number of features compared to the English language, and presents the bulk of open algorithms for them. Often, authors show the high efficiency of algorithms for extracting specific KW only for certain results, but do not provide information about testing the developed algorithms on foreign texts. This article makes an attempt to systematize publications on the problem area of KW extraction, developed methods and algorithms that implement them, and also selected promising areas of research depending on the existing contradictions.

Keyword separation problem

Analysis of the subject area shows that there are different approaches to defining the concept of “keywords”. In addition to the general scientific understanding of KW to determine the structure of the text and give its basic meaning, this process is considered by such scientific and applied sciences as psycholinguistics, communication theory, computer and cognitive linguistics, and computer science [32]. One of the most difficult tasks of text linguistics is the issue of identifying CLs, which different authors call “words-concepts”, “lexical dominants” and “significant symbols” [35].

An analysis of existing publications shows that the definitions of KW in different approaches often coincide, but they are not formal enough. Summarizing many provisions, we can conclude that KW are important for the specific structure of the word in a given text, generally understandable, broad and exemplary, and their set can provide the reader with a high level of description of its content, description and storage. its meanings in memory [36, 32, 28, 14]. KW is used when searching for information, simplifies the description of a certain information resource, and reduces the amount of information required for this.

The concepts of “key word” and “key phrase” (phrase) are considered synonymous by most scientists. But some researchers point to differences in the content of these concepts. Key phrases are combinations of one or more words that can be separated in the text after each other or other linguistic units [19]. In fact, not all words included in key phrases are considered KW. However, it is difficult to express

the main meaning of the content by highlighting individual KW. Therefore, it is necessary to select key phrases in practice. This is close to the issue of creating a list of terms and links to them (back-of book indexes) [24, 29, 31]. The main difference is the length of the list at the output of the algorithm. A document usually consists of units of key phrases, and the length of the list of KW-based terms ranges from ten to one hundred. Creating a list of key phrases is one of the tasks in the subject area under consideration.

As a result of systematization of data from various researchers, a list of necessary properties and functions of KW that are important in modeling and algorithmizing the process of obtaining KW from texts has been determined. Based on this, the KW can be characterized as follows:

- common names [36], object, state/action attribute [35];
- has vocabulary that is important in content, quite generalized in its semantics (at an average level of abstraction), and stylistically neutral [36];
- connected into a network of mutual semantic relationships (intersection of meanings) [32];
- more than half of the thematic component is KW, and with the logical organization of the minimum set of KW, the content practically does not change;
- a set of KW consists of 5–15 [19] or 8–10 words [32], corresponding to human memory, and the text contains 25–30% of KW [35];
- A set of KW determines the contexts of words.

In the process of understanding the text, the KW differs in syntactic position (heading or first sentence), frequency of use, lexical patterns, unusual combinations, synonyms, antonyms, morphological and semantic derivatives [35] (Fig. 1).

Figure 1. Key Features of Keywords

Despite many specialized and interdisciplinary works on KW, a unified methodology for determining KW still does not exist. Experiments have proven that people perform this action intuitively, depending on personality and even gender [34]. This means that it is difficult to develop methods and algorithms for extracting KW for computer technologies. The lack of clearly formalized models and very vague definitions from the point of view of computational linguistics and other engineering disciplines make it difficult to create and validate appropriate tools.

Since the above features of KW appear at several levels of text viewing (morphological, lexical, syntactic and, above all, pragmatic), the relative complexity of methods for their recognition and the multi-stage nature of algorithms that perform bibliographic analysis in General Information Modern algorithms for obtaining KW consist of three stages. (Fig. 2).

Figure 2. Traditional Keyword Research Steps

At the first stage, the text is pre-processed at the grapheme, morpheme and lexical levels. The result is supposed to be presented later in a text-recognizable format. This can be done by auxiliary processes such as graphematic analysis (text tokenization, character removal). Including morphological analysis, lexical normalization (including synonym matching), lemmatization (stemming), part marking (POS tagging), stop word removal (working dictionary) and others [33]. All these processes require the use of certain linguistic frameworks and vocabularies [37, 6]. This step is language specific, meaning that preprocessing differs between languages. Therefore, most of the existing algorithms for obtaining KW must be adapted to the Uzbek language. At this stage, a list of words or phrases corresponding to the KW is formed.

The second step is the actual recognition of the KW (or filtering the initial list). Significant differences in modern algorithms for extracting KW appear at the second stage. After specifying the values of the content of the feature, depending on the chosen approach, they are compared with the standards and a decision is made about whether the word belongs to the set of KW. Depending on the main method of KW extraction, the algorithm can use different linguistic resources: dictionaries, corpora, ontologies. Consequently, this block can be either language-dependent or language-independent.

In the last step, a list of KW is provided instead of the output. The list will have one or another format depending on the user/program settings. Here, list reduction, coloring and sorting, visualization using cognitive graphics methods are performed [26]. Thus, the core of any KW extraction algorithm is a recognition block within the framework of a certain approach, the classification of which describes the content of the subject area.

Classification of keyword extraction methods

Available publications describe to varying degrees the classification of methods for automatically obtaining KW. Most researchers distinguish between statistical methods and methods based on machine learning [2]. Statistical and hybrid KW models and specific methods based on them were considered in the works of the corresponding authors on a similar classification [38, -B. 76–81]. A more detailed classification involves dividing into four layers: those that do not require training in simple statistical methods; linguistic methods; based on machine learning methods and their combinations [23].

The latest existing review on KW extraction presents a classification based on a recognition system, suggesting a choice of linguistic, statistical and hybrid (linguistic) methods [25]. Unfortunately, not all classifications considered reflect the entire range and features of available solutions.

Any KW extraction algorithm actually performs the detection of one or more patterns that divide the input set of words into two classes (key and others). For this reason, it is proposed to use a classification of compatible methods rather than hierarchical ones (Fig. 3). The KW feature set is given below:

- elements of training and types of approaches to its implementation;
- the type of software of the recognition system is determined by the form of information representing the characteristics of the KW;
- type of linguistic resources used to implement the method.

Figure 3. Classification of keyword extraction methods

Based on the presence of training elements, KW extraction is divided into untrained, trained and self-learning methods. Simpler untrained methods involve extracting context-independent knowledge from a single text based on pre-built models and rules. They correspond to corpora of texts that grow in size over time and are functionally uniform in style (for example, scientific articles or regulations). The studied methods use various linguistic resources to adapt decision criteria for recognizing KW. Here it is important to correctly select the KW from the sample used in training. Self-learning is carried out without a teacher or with reinforcement based on passive adaptation. Among the methods, a subclass of self-education can be distinguished.

According to the second criterion of classification (Fig. 3), first of all, it is necessary to distinguish between statistical and structural methods for identifying KW. Statistical methods take into account the relative frequency of occurrence of morphological, lexical, syntactic units and their combinations. This simplifies the generated algorithms. But this is not clear enough, since the frequency response of the KW is not dominant [15]. An element of a document set is the text in it. One of the classic methods of this class is TF-IDF (Term Frequency-Inverse Document Frequency) - calculation for each word measure in the text [5].

Structural methods are based on the idea of a text, which, in turn, is a system of semantically and grammatically related elements of a word, characterized by a set of linguistic features. Therefore, many researchers call this class of methods linguistic. Here, as a first approximation, two subclasses can be distinguished: graph and syntactic (template). Graph-based methods represent words in a text as “vertices” and the relationships between them as “edges”. These relationships may reflect the sequential occurrence of each pair of words in the text, the presence of a dimension within a certain range, and semantic proximity. For the vertices of the resulting graph, centrality measures are calculated and KW is selected according to the boundary criterion. The differences between these methods lie primarily in taking into account the significance of each peak and calculating the relationship between them. Syntactic (template) methods are based on the idea of correct syntactic constructions containing KW in certain positions. In their pure form, such methods are rarely applied to the problem under consideration, but can be used in combination with others.

Neural network methods have recently been applied to the KW extraction problem. The method is based on the generalization of hidden connections between input-output data and the properties of artificial neural networks. However, training and operation of neural networks requires the selection of structural and statistical features of the formation of a data set. Therefore, to obtain the KW, hybrid methods are used, that is, combining elements of the main classes under consideration.

KW extraction algorithms that implement the above methods cannot use any linguistic resources or various types of dictionaries, ontologies and thesauri, text corpora (with or without markup). It should be said that although the above classification is quite sufficient, it is not enough to describe real changes in the area of the topic under consideration.

Review of Keyword Extraction Algorithms

The development of KW models and character recognition theory has changed approaches to automatically extracting KW from text. Based on the dynamics of research, we can conclude that in recent years, the improvement of computer

technologies has increased interest in the topic under consideration and the number of software solutions (Fig. 4).

Figure 4. Dynamics of keyword extraction research

Early ideas about the importance of the frequency factor in KW detection led to the implementation of a statistical approach in algorithms such as KWIC (Key Words In Context) [7]. Research based on these methods is ongoing [10, 27]. Recent modifications of the algorithms combine a statistical approach with learning (where Wikipedia resources are used as a corpus) [11, 30]. Algorithms that implement purely structural methods are predominantly graph-oriented algorithms, the first publications of which date back to the beginning of the century [13, 9]. In a short time, more advanced modifications of such algorithms appeared. Their characteristics are given below.

The language-independent graph-oriented algorithm TextRank was proposed in 2004 [12]. It is built on the popular PageRank web page ranking algorithm. The importance of a graph vertex is calculated based on the importance of its neighboring vertices. Here, any connection between lexical units can be considered as an edge of the graph. KW selection is an adjacency or co-occurrence relationship determined by the distance between words.

If the vertices correspond to lexical units of width $2 \leq N \leq 10$, then the two vertices are adjacent. Lexical filtering can be used before inserting (adding) vertices to the graph. After constructing the graph, the importance of the vertices is calculated, ranked, and the first 5-20 are stored for further processing as potential KW. Adjacent KW sequences form KW junctions, and the rest are taken as normal KW. Rake's algorithm [14] first creates a list of potential KWs using a dictionary that separates given phrases, and then builds a graph with the vertices of individual words. A special feature of such a graph is that the vertices of the graph can be represented by the same words. The following indicators of importance are determined for a word: frequency of occurrence of a peak, level of a peak, ratio of level to frequency. The importance of a potential keyword phrase is calculated as the sum of the values of each word included in it. The first third of the list of vertices, arranged in descending order of importance, is selected as the KW for this text. In the DegExt algorithm, stop words are first removed and then a graph is constructed [6]. Arcs between vertices are drawn only for adjacent words in any sentence that are not separated by punctuation. The highest level peaks correspond to those selected for KW. To extract keywords, you need to select from a list (of a certain length) adjacent sequences of words that appear in the same sentence. The importance of each phrase is calculated as the average rank of its constituent words. Compared to TextRank, this algorithm is computationally simpler. The authors used it to isolate a large number of KW (~15).

Similar to the DegExt algorithm, seven vertex centralization measures are considered in three categories: degree, proximity, and betweenness [17]. The best results in KW retrieval were achieved using normal length medial centering.

Other graph algorithms differ from the above by using information such as word position and length, and text layout and format. [27, 9, 18, 21].

In the 2000s, machine learning became widely used to solve the KW extraction problem, and the number of these algorithms exceeded the number of untrained algorithms. First of all, these are teacher-taught algorithms based on hybrid structural-statistical methods. Another study described a trained GenEx algorithm combined with

a genetic algorithm for KW extraction [19]. The main features of KW extraction are the frequencies of words and the positions of their first appearance in the text.

Russian scientists combined two methods in their research: a measure of semantic proximity calculated based on Wikipedia and an algorithm for detecting groups in Girvan-Newman networks [28]. First, all possible n-grams are extracted from the text and Wikipedia articles are found for each of them. Ambiguities are resolved by searching for articles with the greatest semantic similarity to the context. Then a semantic graph is constructed, where the weight of an edge is equal to the numerical value of the semantic similarity of words. Finally, the graph is divided into ranked groups (by density and information content). Key terms are the terms in the groups (from first to third) with the highest rank. The algorithm was tested by the authors on English texts.

Other hybrid learning-based algorithms use Bayesian classification [22, 3, 20], conditional random fields (CRF) methods [23], and support vector machines [4]. It's important to note that self-learning solutions are relatively new. First of all, these include neural networks [16] and self-organizing Kohonen maps [1]. In general, despite the constant improvement of classical statistical and structural algorithms for KW detection, the main focus of developers is on the field of trained hybrid solutions based on text corpora.

Comparative descriptions of the main algorithms for extracting KW.

Currently, the following properties of KW extraction algorithms, available in many sources, are being considered: accuracy (P-Precision), recall (R-Recall) and a measure of the relationship between accuracy and completeness (F-measure) (Tab.1).

Table 1. Comparative description of the main algorithms for extracting KW

Algorithm	P, %	R, %	F, %	Tested	Linguis tic diversit y	Notes
TF-IDF (1972)	23.2	28.1	25.4	Wan X.	+	
KeyGraph (1998)	36,0	36,0	36,0	Matsuo Y.	No	
Witten I. (1999)	19.0	40,0	25.7	Sakar K.	No	The number of keywords is 10.
GenEx (2000)	11-29	-	-	Vanyushkin	+	The number of KW on texts on different topics is 4-16.
Xult A. (2003)	25.2	51.7	33.9	Vanyushkin	No	
Matsuo Y. (2004)	42.0	46,0	43.9	Matsuo Y.	No	
TextRank (2004)	31.2	43.1	36.2	Vanyushkin	+	The number of KW on texts on different topics is 4-16
Wi-Fi (2007)	94.3	70.5	80.7	Vanyushkin	+	Wikipedia is required to launch
DegExt (2008)	75,0	15.0	24.0	Vanyushkin	+	Document database DUC 2002. 30 keywords.
Chjan C. (2008)	66.3	41.9	51.2	Vanyushkin	No	
Grineva M. (2009)	52,0	73,0	60,0	Vanyushkin	+	Wikipedia is required to launch
ExpandRank (2008)	28.6	35.2	31.6	Vanyushkin	No	The number of basic phrases is 10.
Rake (2010)	33.7	41.5	37.2	Vanyushkin	+	1/3 of the number of words after the filter is the number of KW.
Sakar K. (2010)	22.0	46,0	29.7	Vanyushkin	No	The number of basic phrases is 10.
SemanticRank (2010)	42.1	53.2	47,0	Vanyushkin	No	The number of basic phrases is 20.
Korshunov A (2011)	40,0	68.6	50.5	Vanyushkin	No	Wikipedia is required to launch

Summary

Currently, algorithms cannot achieve 100% accuracy for two main reasons. Firstly, the manually selected KW is not always present in the text, so the problem is not in extracting the KW, but in its generation. Secondly, the result depends on the number of KW, which in most algorithms is set regardless of the text size. Therefore, it is necessary to develop an objective and universal criterion for assessing the quality of work of KW extraction algorithms.

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